

Studies in 4-Hydroxycoumarins: Part III γ -Pyrone from 4-Hydroxycoumarins

V. N. Dholakia and K. N. Trivedi

4-Hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin on Claisen condensation with ethyl oxalate gave the β -diketone (Id) which cyclised to 4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IIb). 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-3-acetylcoumarin, on similar condensation with ethyl benzoate and ethyl oxalate gave (IIa) and (IIc) respectively. 3-Propionyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin and 3-propionyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave (IId) and (IIe) respectively.

In part II¹, Claisen condensation of different 4-hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin was carried out to give corresponding β -diketones which were subsequently cyclised to corresponding coumarino- γ -pyrones. This work is now extended and the condensation of different 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives has been carried out with ethyl benzoate and ethyl oxalate and the β -diketones (I) thus formed are cyclised to corresponding coumarino- γ -pyrone derivatives (II).

3-Acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ic) was condensed with ethyl benzoate to give 3-benzoylacetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ib) which underwent cyclisation with 50% sulphuric acid to 2-phenyl-9-methyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIa).

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| <p>I. a. R = R₁ = R₂ = H
 b. R = -COC₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = -CH₃
 c. R = R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₃
 d. R = -COCOOC₂H₅, R₁ = R₂ = H
 e. R = -COCOOC₂H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₃
 f. R = CH₃, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₃
 g. R = CH₃, R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = H.</p> | <p>II. a. R = C₆H₅, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = CH₃
 b. R = -COOH, R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H
 c. R = COOH, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = CH₃
 d. R = R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H, R₃ = CH₃
 e. R = R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = OCH₃, R₃ = H</p> |
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3-Acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (Ia) and 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ic) were condensed with ethyl oxalate to give 3-oxalylacetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (Id) and 3-oxalylacetyl 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ie) respectively. These were cyclised with 50% sulphuric acid to give 4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c) benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IIb)

1. V. N. Dholakia, M. G. Parekh and K. N. Trivedi. *Australian J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 2345.

and 9-methyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IIc). Attempts to decarboxylate these acids by heating above their m.ps. or with copper and quinoline were unsuccessful.

3-Propionyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin² (If) on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave 2,3,9-trimethyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran (IId). 4-Hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin on Friedel-Crafts propionylation with propionic acid and phosphorus oxychloride gave 3-propionyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (Ig.). This on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation afforded 2,3-dimethyl-8-methoxy-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIe).

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Benzoylacetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ib): A mixture of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (1.0 g.), ethyl benzoate (25 ml.) and pulverised sodium (1.0 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180° for 5 hr. After the completion of reaction little alcohol was added to decompose unreacted sodium and then added to water. It was ether extracted and aqueous layer was acidified. The separated product was filtered, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 168°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 70.72; H, 4.47. C₁₉H₁₄O₅ requires C, 70.80; H, 4.38%).

2-Phenyl-9-methyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIa): 3-Benzoylacetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (0.4 g.) was heated with alcoholic sulphuric acid (50 ml.; 50%) on a sand bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and the separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 275°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 74.69; H, 4.05. C₁₉H₁₂O₄ requires C, 74.29; H, 3.97%).

3-Oxalylacetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (Id): A mixture of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (1.0 g.), ethyl oxalate (12 ml.) and pulverised sodium (1.0 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 6 hrs. After the completion of reaction little alcohol was added to decompose unreacted sodium and then added to ice and water. It was then ether extracted and aqueous layer was acidified, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 168°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 59.14; H, 3.85. C₁₅H₁₂O₇ requires C, 59.21; H, 3.98%).

4,5-Dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IIb): 3-Oxalylacetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (0.5 g.) was heated with sulphuric acid (25 ml.; 50%) on a sand bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and the separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 270°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 60.22; H, 2.05. C₁₃H₆O₆ requires C, 60.47; H, 2.34%).

3-Oxalylacetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ie): A mixture of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (1.0 g.), ethyl oxalate (12 ml.) and pulverised sodium (1.0 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured into ice and water and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified and the separated product was filtered, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 169°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 60.14; H, 4.04. C₁₆H₁₁O₇ requires C, 60.38; H, 4.43%).

9-*Methyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran-2-carboxylic acid (IIc)*: 3-Oxalyl-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (0.5 g.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (25 ml.; 50%) on a sand bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured into ice and water and the separated product was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 262°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 61.52; H, 2.88. $C_{14}H_8O_6$ requires C, 61.77; H, 2.96%).

2,3,9-*Trimethyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzopyran (II d)*: A mixture of 3-propionyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (1.0 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (3.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml.) was heated in an oil bath at 140–60° for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice and water. The separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 247°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 70.00; H, 4.30. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.30; H, 4.72%).

3-*Propionyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (I g)*: A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (3.0 g.), propionic acid (15 ml.) and phosphorus oxychloride (6 ml.) was refluxed on a wire gauze for 45 mins. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and water. The separated product was filtered, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 168°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 62.91; H, 4.67. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.90; H, 4.87%).

2,3-*Dimethyl-8-methoxy-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c) benzopyran (II e)*: A mixture of 3-propionyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (1.0 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (3.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml.) was heated in an oil bath at 140–60° for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and water and the separated product was filtered, dried and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 228°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 66.05; H, 4.47. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.17; H, 4.44%).

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Chemistry Department,
Faculty of Science,
M. S. University of Baroda,
Baroda.

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